

A bibliometric analysis of feature selection techniques: trends, innovations, and future directions

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ABSTRACT

Feature selection techniques have become increasingly important in addressing the challenges of high dimensionality in machine learning and other artificial intelligence domains. In this study, we present a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of research on feature selection techniques over the past decade, focusing on mapping the intellectual structure, identifying emerging trends, and highlighting productive collaborations in the field. Using merged data from Scopus and Web of Science databases, we collected and analyzed 2,079 relevant documents published between 2014 and 2024, applying citation analysis, co-authorship networks, and keyword co-occurrence mapping. Our findings reveal that feature selection methodologies including supervised, unsupervised, and hybrid approaches across filter, wrapper, and embedded techniques, have been widely applied across various domains. The authors who have most contributed to the development of these methods are primarily affiliated with institutions in China, India, and the USA. The insights provided by this analysis offer researchers and practitioners a valuable foundation for guiding future research directions in feature selection.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the era of big data, the explosion of multidimensional data has heightened the need for efficient machine learning algorithms while exacerbating the "curse of dimensionality" [1]. This phenomenon, where adding features leads to data dispersion, complicates model generalization and increases the risk of overfitting [2]. To address these challenges, feature selection has become a crucial strategy in artificial intelligence and machine learning, aiming to identify the most relevant variables to improve model efficiency [3], thereby establishing itself as a prominent research field [4]. The field encompasses various methodologies, including supervised, unsupervised, and hybrid approaches, with selection strategies categorized into wrapper, filter, and embedded methods, each offering specific advantages and limitations [3], [5]. Recently, significant progress has been made in integrating deep learning techniques for feature selection, promising better management of complex and large-scale data [6], [7]. Moreover, the emergence of adaptive methods capable of dynamically adjusting feature selection based on evolving data opens up new perspectives for more robust and flexible models [8].

The versatility of feature selection is demonstrated across diverse domains. In healthcare, particularly oncology, these techniques have revolutionized cancer detection and diagnostic precision [9], [10].

The financial sector harnesses them for risk assessment and insurance optimization [11], while manufacturing industries benefit from their application in predictive maintenance [12]. The technology sector has integrated these methods into intrusion detection systems and natural language processing applications [13], [14], and bioinformatics leverages them for gene expression analysis and protein structure prediction [15]. Additionally, transportation systems have achieved significant improvements in traffic optimization and travel time prediction through these techniques [16].

The exponential growth of scientific literature has necessitated the employment of systematic methods for analyzing research developments. Bibliometric analysis, encompassing citation analysis, co-authorship networks, and keyword co-occurrence patterns, provide a robust framework for evaluating scientific output and research evolution [17]. These analytical approaches, enhanced by recent developments in bibliometric tools, enable sophisticated examination of large-scale scientific data, offering comprehensive insights into research dynamics [18]. While existing studies have provided valuable insights into specific aspects of feature selection, such as optimization algorithms in healthcare applications [19] and microarray research trends [20], there remains a critical need for a comprehensive understanding of this rapidly evolving field.

Our study addresses this research gap through a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of feature selection literature spanning the past decade. This analysis aims to map the field's intellectual structure, identify emerging research frontiers, and provide evidence-based insights to guide future investigations. The paper is structured as follows: First, we present a detailed description of our bibliometric methodology, encompassing data collection processes and analytical tools. Subsequently, we present our findings, followed by an in-depth discussion of the results. The paper concludes with a synthesis of key insights, while acknowledging methodological limitations and proposing future research directions in this domain.

2. METHOD

Despite the variety of literature databases available, such as Dimensions [21], Lens, PubMed [22], and Cochrane Library. For this study, Scopus and Web of Science were chosen as they are the most comprehensive and commonly referenced multidisciplinary databases [23]. Additionally, based on suggestions [24] and recommendations [23], these two selected databases complement each other, especially when comparing various fields, institutions, countries, or languages. Therefore, this study will focus on merging the two main databases: Scopus and Web of Science.

The bibliometric data collection process took place on September 25, 2024. All searches were conducted on the same day to prevent bias from daily database updates. The research study aimed to identify keywords present in the articles' titles, keywords, or abstracts. The following topical query was performed: ("Feature selection" OR "Dimensionality reduction" OR "Attribute selection") AND ("Supervised learning" OR "Unsupervised learning" OR "Machine learning" OR "Deep learning") AND ("Statistical methods" OR "PCA" OR "Principal component analysis" OR "Correlation-based" OR "Chi-square" OR "Mutual information" OR "ANOVA" OR "Variance threshold"). This resulted in 2088 documents in Scopus and 1,328 documents in Web of Science. Figure 1 shows the identification of studies via databases.

Figure 1. Identification of studies via databases

The PRISMA flowchart [25], as depicted in Figure 1, was utilized to select only 2,079 eligible papers. Initially, all document types: articles, proceeding papers, and reviews were included. Then, records published outside the period of 2014-2024 were removed. The latest version of R (4.4.1) [26] was used, along with the bibliometric package, to merge, screen, analyze, and map the downloaded bibliographic data [27]. A “.xlsx” Excel file was uploaded to the Biblioshiny, a web-based graphical user interface included in bibliometric [28]. Data analysis was supported by downloading Excel (.csv) and image (.png) files, which were processed in line with the study’s objectives.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we present the findings of our bibliometric analysis, utilizing two distinct approaches. First, we conducted a descriptive analysis to gather statistical information. Next, we employed scientific mapping to explore the conceptual structure, focusing on key terms and the social network among authors who have contributed to the development of feature selection techniques. This section presents detailed statistics on yearly research output, average citations per year, and identifies the most productive authors, institutions, countries, publications, and keywords. It also sheds light on the most frequently cited sources and authors.

3.1. Descriptive analysis

3.1.1. Key retrieved information

Table 1 provides an overview of the main bibliometric indicators associated with feature selection techniques across various domains of artificial intelligence. The table summarizes information such as document types, publication sources, authorship statistics, keyword frequencies, and patterns of research collaboration. According to the data, 2,079 documents have been published on this topic, the majority being journal articles (1,365) and conference papers (539). Notably, the annual growth rate is negative (-27.8%), suggesting a decline in scientific output on feature selection techniques in recent years. This trend will be examined more closely in the following sections to better understand its implications.

3.1.2. Annual scientific production over the years

Figure 2 illustrates the annual scientific production over the years. Starting from 2014, a steady increase in output is observed until 2020, followed by a moderate rise through 2021 and 2022, reaching a peak in 2023. This sustained growth may be attributed to the increasing complexity of feature selection challenges in machine learning and other artificial intelligence applications, as well as to the dedicated efforts of researchers. However, this upward trend is followed by a noticeable decline in 2024, as also noted in Table 1.

Table 1. Main statistical information

Category	Description	Results
Main information about data	Timespan	2014:2025
	Sources (journals and books)	1,091
	Documents	2,079
	Annual growth rate %	-27.8
	Document average age	2.61
	Average citations per doc	16.32
	References	16328
Document contents	Keywords plus (ID)	11144
	Author's keywords (DE)	5055
Authors	Authors	6,122
	Authors of single-authored docs	65
Authors collaboration	Single-authored docs	110
	Co-Authors per doc	4.18
	International co-authorships %	4.521
Document types	Article	1,365
	Article article	9
	Article conference paper	4
	Article review	1
	Article; early access	7
	Article; proceedings paper	3
	Article; retracted publication	4
	Conference paper	539
	Conference paper article	2
	Conference review	40
	Conference review article	1
	Proceeding's paper	34
	Review	69
	Review article	1

Figure 2. Annual scientific production over the years

3.1.3. Most relevant sources and affiliations

The analysis of publication sources and author affiliations offers insight into the key venues and institutions contributing to feature selection research. Figure 3 displays the ten most relevant sources, with IEEE Access leading the list with 60 published documents. Table 2 presents the most productive institutions, revealing a concentration of research efforts in Asia, particularly China and Saudi Arabia. These findings reflect the geographical and institutional dynamics shaping current research trends in the field.

Figure 3. Most relevant sources

Table 2. Affiliations

Affiliation	Articles
Northwestern Polytechnical University	25
King Saud University	24
University of California	20
Comsats University Islamabad	18
Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University	18
Shenzhen University	17
Guangdong University of Technology	15
Najran University	15
Xinjiang University	14

3.1.4. Statistics by country

Tables 3 and 4 summarize the scientific output by country in the field of feature selection techniques. China, India, and the USA lead in publication volume, with 696, 514, and 330 documents,

respectively. At the regional level, Asia accounts for the majority of contributions (1,437 publications), reflecting the continent's growing investment in artificial intelligence research. The Americas, mainly represented by the USA and Canada, contribute a total of 844 documents. These figures highlight Asia's central role in driving global research output, while also illustrating the strong presence of North America in the field.

Table 3. Countries' productivity

Region	Frequency
China	696
India	514
USA	330
Canada	95
Saudi Arabia	95
UK	84
Iran	70
Australia	62
South Korea	62
Spain	55

Table 4. Most cited countries

Country	Total citations	Average article citations
China	8751	21.10
USA	3632	24.70
India	3252	9.90
United Kingdom	1801	40.90
Korea	1495	28.80
Saudi Arabia	992	18.00
Italy	876	38.10
Iran	824	24.20
Spain	721	34.30
Turkey	608	21.00

Figure 4 presents the research productivity trends of five countries—Canada, China, India, Saudi Arabia, and the USA. The results show a steady rise in publication output for China, India, and the USA between 2014 and 2024. As the study concluded in September 2024, data for the final months of the year are not included, leaving the continuation of this trend uncertain. By contrast, Saudi Arabia and Canada display only moderate growth in their research output over the same period.

Figure 4. Countries' production over time

3.1.5. Author productivity through Lotka's law

Lotka's law was applied to analyze author productivity. Proposed by Alfred James Lotka in 1926 [29], this statistical principle describes how scientific output is distributed among authors: a small proportion accounts for the majority of publications, while most authors contribute only a few works. This law can be mathematically formulated as in (1).

$$N(x) = \frac{N(1)}{x^n} \quad (1)$$

Where $N(x)$ represent the number of authors who have published a total of x papers, $N(1)$ number of authors who have published just one paper and n is typically around 2. However subsequent research has shown that n can vary depending on the field of discipline. Figure 5 illustrates that, in the field of feature selection, most authors have contributed only one or two publications, while very few have published extensively. The observed distribution follows Lotka's law, indicating that a minority of authors contribute a disproportionately large number of studies.

Figure 5. Distribution of author productivity based on Lotka's law

3.1.6. Statistics by documents

Among the 2,079 documents related to feature selection techniques, this subsection highlights the ten most globally cited papers, as shown in Table 5. These publications span diverse domains such as remote sensing, image processing, bioinformatics, and medical diagnostics, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of feature selection research. Chen *et al.* [30] discussed deep learning-based classification for hyperspectral data, using a hybrid approach to extract high-level features, and has received 1,949 global citations, illustrating its long-standing influence. Babenko *et al.* [31] explored neural codes for image retrieval, employing principal component analysis for feature extraction, and has accumulated 950 citations. Although most of these papers are not among the most recent, their consistently high citation rates underscore their foundational role and ongoing relevance in the development of feature selection methodologies.

Figure 6 presents the keywords most commonly appearing in publications on feature selection techniques. "deep learning" is the most common keyword, appearing 11% of the time, suggesting that many of these techniques are applied in deep learning contexts. This is followed by "principal component analysis", "dimensionality reduction", "learning system" and "feature extraction".

Table 5. Top ten global cited documents in feature selection

Paper	Total citations	Total citations per year
Chen <i>et al.</i> [30]	1949	177.18
Babenko <i>et al.</i> [31]	950	86.36
Chen <i>et al.</i> [32]	934	93.40
Wang <i>et al.</i> [33]	663	73.67
Gromski <i>et al.</i> [34]	583	58.30
Nanni <i>et al.</i> [35]	413	51.63
Valletta <i>et al.</i> [36]	333	41.63
Sharma and Sharma [37]	332	47.43
Chang <i>et al.</i> [38]	331	47.29
Bhandary <i>et al.</i> [39]	326	65.20

Figure 8. Thematic map: authors' keywords

3.3. Social structure

This section examines the collaboration networks of authors, institutions, and countries involved in feature selection research. In the three diagrams presented, nodes correspond to authors, institutions, or countries, and the edges illustrate their cooperative links. Figure 9 illustrates clusters of co-authors working together, with authors Wang [33], [40]–[45], Wang [46], [47], and Wang [33], [48]–[50] having the largest number of collaborators in producing documents on feature selection techniques.

Figure 9. Authors' collaboration network

Figure 10 highlights that China has the highest level of collaboration, as well as the largest number of published documents, consistent with previous statistics. In terms of affiliations, Figure 11 maps the co-affiliation network of institutions. Institutions like COMSATS University Islamabad, King Saud University, and Shenzhen University demonstrate strong collaboration among their affiliated authors.

Figure 10. Countries' collaboration network

Figure 11. Institutions' collaboration network

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, we conducted a detailed bibliometric analysis to examine the development and impact of feature selection techniques within the fields of machine learning and artificial intelligence. Our analysis drew from 2,079 documents published between 2014 and 2024 in the Scopus and Web of Science databases. To our knowledge, this is one of the most comprehensive bibliometric studies on feature selection, providing insights into key emerging trends and collaborations across diverse research domains. Our findings indicate a substantial increase in research output from 2014 to 2023, reflecting the growing importance of feature selection techniques in addressing challenges associated with high-dimensional data. Countries such as China, India, and the USA emerged as leading contributors to the field, highlighting their significant role in advancing feature selection methodologies. While this study provides valuable insights, it is essential to recognize that the specific keywords used to retrieve data may have influenced our results. Future research could refine and expand the scope by incorporating alternative keywords. Additionally, since this analysis relied on Scopus and Web of Science data, subsequent studies could broaden the perspective by including other databases to capture a more extensive range of contributions to feature selection research.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Oumaima Semmar	✓	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓				✓
Wissal El Habti	✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓					
Donalson Wilson	✓		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓			
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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The bibliometric data supporting the findings of this study were obtained from the Scopus and Web of Science databases, which are subject to subscription access. The derived dataset generated after screening, cleaning, and merging these records is available from the corresponding author [WEH] upon reasonable request.

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